

Speculation on Bound Wavefunction Humps as Information

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It is known that a quantum bound state wavefunction may have humps which are linked to the energy state n (e.g. a particle in a box with infinite walls or an oscillator). $W(x)W(x)$ (bound) represents a probability distribution. For a fixed variance, a Gaussian distribution maximizes entropy. This is the wavefunction of the ground state of an oscillator, but adding structured phonons not only increases the energy of the state (i.e. moves it from the ground to an excited level), but gives structure (humps) to the distribution. We argue that these humps represent information about the way in which the state may decay. Thus quantum bound states differ from maximized entropy states subject to an overall constraint linked to say energy etc. There seems to be a correlation between higher energy and spatial information which ultimately follows from the momentum-spatial part of the classical action: px (from $-Et+px$) being held constant.

Free Particle Action

In (1) we argued that one may write the relativistic or nonrelativistic classical actions $A = -m_0 t \sqrt{1-v^2/c^2}$ ($c=1$) and $t \cdot \frac{1}{2}mv^2$ in terms of $v=x/t$ and vary x and t independently to yield:

$$dA/dx \text{ partial} = p \text{ ((1a)) and } dA/dt = -E \text{ ((1b))}$$

Thus p is linked to an operator which is of the form of $1/\text{Length}$. We also noted that the idea of A constant seems to be important. In particular:

$$dA = p dx - E dt = 0 \rightarrow dx/dt = E/p = \text{velocity of a classical wave ((2a))}$$

$$dA = dp x - dE t = 0 \rightarrow dE/dp = x/t = \text{velocity of a classical relativistic particle ((2b))}$$

If one holds the momentum-space part of A constant then : $px = \text{constant} \text{ ((3))}$

This suggests that: $p = \text{constant} / x$ i.e. there is a characteristic length for each p which is inverse to the size of p . At this point no mention has been made of quantum mechanics or probability distributions. To bring in quantum mechanics, one may establish eigenvalue equations from ((1a)) and ((1b)) i.e.

$$-i d/dx \text{ partial} \exp(iA) = p \exp(iA) \text{ ((4a)) and } i d/dt \text{ partial} \exp(iA) = E \exp(iA) \text{ ((4b))}$$

$\exp(iA) = \exp(ipx - iEt)$. ((1a)) and ((1b)) follow from x and t being treated as independent which is the opposite viewpoint of classical mechanics. The question is how may one interpret $\exp(iA)$. It is almost as if $\cos(px)$ and $\sin(px)$ represent a set of probability distributions each bounded by values of zero e.g. $\cos(p x_a) = \cos(p x_b) = 0$. The larger p , the smaller $x_b - x_a$ and the higher the resolution. We argue that this means more spatial information. This result seems to follow from insisting on a constant momentum-spatial portion of the classical action i.e. $px = \text{constant}$.

It may be noted that for classical elastic particle scattering $e_1 + e_2 = e_3 + e_4 = E$. Given E , one does not know e_i or e_j . Any that sum to E are fine. Thus there is a loss of information. For free particles $px = A$ (spatial) = constant is similar. Any p, L set whose product is A constant is fine. This seems to be the root of $p, L = 1/p$ pairs, but this suggests nonlocality because L is a length range not a point. This is different from classical mechanics, but similar to classical waves. The eigenvalue equation leads to a set of probability distributions $\exp(ipx)$, but integrating $\exp(-ip_1 x)$ $\exp(ip_2 x)$ is constant if $p_1 = p_2$ and 0 otherwise so one has an orthogonal function. Thus the $p, 1/p$ pairs not only represent different energy-length resolution of information pairs, but also contain inherent orthogonality so that each $\exp(ipx)$ is distinct from others if one integrates over x i.e. considers nonlocality which part of a wave picture (even a probability wave one).

Thus the higher energy leads to both increased spatial information (resolution), but also to orthogonality. It is almost as if an increased energy is the price to pay for a wavefunction orthogonal to all with lower eigenenergies. This wavefunction carries information about the discrete wavefunctions which came before it (i.e. has one more hump than the others at least for an oscillator or particle in a box with infinite potential walls) in order to ensure that it is orthogonal to all.

Probability Distributions

One may see from ((4a)) and ((4b)) that one may take derivatives twice and establish the Klein-Gordon and Schrodinger equations from classical energy conservation equations:

$$EE = (pc)(pc) + (mocc)(mocc) \quad \text{and} \quad E_{\text{nonrel}} = pp/2m \quad ((5))$$

For both cases, $pp = -\hbar/dx \hbar/dx \exp(iA)$. If a potential is present, one may suggest that $\exp(iA)$ becomes a complex function $W(x,t)$ and write the Schrodinger equation:

$$-\hbar^2/2m \hbar/dx \hbar/dx \text{partial } W(x,t) + V(x) W(x,t) = E W(x,t) \quad ((6))$$

This still begs the question: What is $W(x,t)$? Born suggested it is linked to a probability namely $P(x) = W^*(x)W(x)$. For a bound state $W(x)$ is real. This seems to suggest that $W(x,t)$ and hence also $\exp(iA)$ is already a kind of probability distribution. In fact, each hump of $W(x)$ looks like a distribution.

To see this more clearly in terms of probability distributions familiar in classical physics, consider the ground state wavefunction of the quantum oscillator:

$$W(x) = \exp(-a xx) \quad \text{where } a = .5 \text{ sqrt}(km) \quad ((7))$$

This is of the form of the spatial density of a classical ideal gas with an oscillator potential. Furthermore a Gaussian maximizes Shannon's entropy $-\sum_i P(i) \ln[P(i)]$ for a fixed variance. Thus there seems to be a kind of disorder or lack of information about the ground state oscillator wavefunction.

Link with Classical Physics

The bound wavefunction $W(x)$ as well as the probability $P(x)$ differ greatly from classical mechanical notions, but $-1/2m \frac{d}{dx} \frac{dW}{dx} / W$ does not, it is equal to $KE_{\text{classical}}(x)$. Thus the curvature of the distribution leads to a nonclassical $W(x)$ and thus $P(x)$, yet it is this curvature which is required to create the classical quantity $KE(x)$ (kinetic energy). In other words, classical deterministic kinetic energy expressed as curvature defines the quantum distribution which is a statistical quantity. It is almost as if the quantum spatial distribution $W(x)$ must be established in order to create an average classical scenario $KE(x) + V(x) = E_n$ where $KE(x) = -1/2m \frac{d}{dx} \frac{dW}{dx} / W$. This is almost like a classical wave scenario where perturbations to the medium are necessary to create a wave i.e. an energy-momentum which moves at a constant velocity, but does not have a rest mass.

If one considers the quantum oscillator, an excited state should be longer in spatial range than the ground state. Classically one has $E_{\text{excited}} = .5k A^2$ where A is the amplitude. Quantum mechanically, the majority of the probability $P(x)$ will be within $\pm A$. Thus an excited state is extended. At the same time, $KE(0)$ is larger because the extra potential energy is now all kinetic energy (classically). Thus the curvature and the slope of $W(x)$ must become sharper. With an extended probability region, this suggests an extra hump (or more) entering the region. For the SHO oscillator one extra hump appears in $W_n(x)W_n(x)$ as one adds a phonon. Thus we argue that the spatial humps keep track of the energy added and also of possible decay results.

For a particle in a box with infinite potential walls the same is true except that the length of the box L remains constant. Thus a spatial memory seems to be created which is linked to the energy jumps which have occurred.

Each quantum hump which is created in $W(x)W(x)$ is like a probability distribution over a certain x range. $W(x)$ is also similar to such a distribution. The separate humps are not Gaussians, but very crudely mimic them although they drop to zero much more quickly. Thus one dimensional space (for a 1D problem) is broken into separate regions each with its own probability distribution. The classical kinetic energy $KE(x) = E_n - V(x)$ is nonzero yet it is equivalent to curvature of a spatial probability distribution and so forces it to bend or curve downward to zero meaning the probability to find the particle approaches zero even though $KE(x)$ is the classical velocity. Density $P(x) = W(x)W(x)$ multiplied by $KE(x)$, however, approaches zero.

Curvature

The idea of curvature being linked to kinetic energy seems to follow from the momentum-spatial portion of A , i.e. px , being constant. Thus there is a small distance $1/p$ associated with a large p . If one wishes to have a periodic spatial curve, it will repeat itself every $1/p$ units of length. For a small distance this means a steep slope i.e. high bending. For the eigenvalue solution $\exp(ipx)$ one sees the curvature goes as $-p^2 \exp(ipx)$ so high p means high curvature. For a free particle $\exp(-ipx)\exp(ipx)$ is 1 so this curvature does not appear to be important, but it becomes so if there is interference. Even for the free particle, it seems as if it is linked to the motion itself i.e. the particle cannot move without creating two distributions $\cos(px)$ and $\sin(px)$ (orthogonal) which have low spatial probability at certain regions even though the

object is moving with a constant momentum. For a free particle, density $P(x)=1$ and both $KE_{\text{classical}}(x) = -1/2m \frac{d}{dx} \frac{d}{dx} \exp(ipx) / \exp(ipx)$ and $P(x) KE(x)$ are $p^2/2m$. This result is due to both dimensions of $\exp(ipx)$ contributing. If interference occurs i.e. one adds $\exp(ipx) + \exp(-ipx)$, one only sees one dimension and it is as if physical density and kinetic energy density disappear in places i.e. one has a hump or two slit interference type of pattern. The kinetic energy itself $-1/2m \frac{d}{dx} \frac{dW}{dx} / W$, however, does not have this issue. For a bound system with a potential, it is also interference which creates the density humps of $P(x)$.

For a classical wave, a density pattern is established (e.g. density for a sound wave), but the ultimate goal is to have an energy disturbance propagate with $dA=0 = p dx - E dt$. Thus the density from this point of view is not important (i.e. it is real, but it is a detail). All that matters is that there is energy propagation at constant speed equal to E/p (sound in this case). For the quantum case of a particle in a potential $V(x)$, one wishes to create an overall average $KE(x)$ which matches the classical result. In other words there is a $v_{\text{rms}}(x)$ which is the classical velocity. Like the classical wave, it does not matter if a spatial density is created in order to achieve $KE(x)=E_n-V(x)$. The spatial density, like in the classical wave case, may be linked to interference and is physically observable. This spatial density, however, may contain information which is not present in $.5 m v_{\text{rms}}(x)v_{\text{rms}}(x)$ in other words it contains information about the discrete nature of the E_n 's. For a given E_n , $.5m v_{\text{rms}}(x)v_{\text{rms}}(x)$ is completely classical.

Energy as Information?

The energy levels of a quantum oscillator are $E_n = \hbar \omega (n+.5)$ where $\omega=\sqrt{k/m}$. Thus it is said that one phonon is added at a time to create higher energy levels. Phonons carry energy and are linked to a particular wavelength and frequency. The quantum spatial distribution $W(x)$ seems to retain information about this energy added as argued above. The ground state oscillator is a Gaussian i.e. has the least information (most entropy for a fixed variance). One might think that the first excited state might also be a Gaussian with a wider variance to account for the greater amplitude. This would also suggest maximum entropy for a given variance, but this is not a solution of the Schrodinger equation. As argued above a Gaussian with a wider variance is at odds with a higher curvature due to higher kinetic energy. The quantum system seems to build a memory of energy in terms of spatial humps in $P(x)$ at least for the oscillator and particle in a box with infinite potential walls. This somewhat ordered information carrying system contains the information needed to predict the number of possible immediate decays which is $n-1$. It also ensures orthogonality of different energy wavefunctions.

Just as the single free particle $\exp(ipx)$ for which a higher p means a smaller wavelength and hence better resolution or more information, it seems higher energy means more information. For the free particle, however, one does not think in terms of decay because any p and corresponding wavelength are allowed. Only for a particle in a box with infinite walls for which $W(x) = A \sin(pave x)$ does one see the "humps" represent information as the levels are discrete.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that holding the momentum-spatial part of the classical action $A = -Et + px$ constant i.e. px constant leads to different x values for different p 's in an inverse manner. High p means high kinetic energy and small L (wavelength) or high resolution. We argue that this is increased information so higher energy seems to be equivalent to more information. Using A one sees that $dA/dx = p$. Writing this as an eigenvalue equation yields: $-i\hbar d/dx \exp(iA) = p \exp(iA)$ and a similar result for E . $\exp(ipx)$ thus appears as a set of spatial probability-like distributions. Short wavelengths means each distribution is restricted to a small range. If the range becomes very small there may not be enough resolution to distinguish the drop in probabilities (i.e. where $\cos(px)$ or $\sin(px)$) hit zero and one only sees the maxima i.e. one has a classical scenario.

For a bound particle with a potential, $W(x)$ is real and may have humps (particle in a box with infinite potential walls or oscillator). The curvature of $W(x)$ leads to kinetic energy based on a classical conservation of energy law i.e. $KE(x) + V(x) = E_n$. Thus classical physics is driving the overall result, but underlying this is a set of probability distributions (much like the medium perturbations caused by a classical wave). Each distribution is bounded by $W(x_a) = 0 = W(x_b)$ i.e. there humps. The higher the energy, the more the humps and the smaller their range i.e. the smaller $x_b - x_a$. For a particle in a box (infinite potential walls) or the oscillator each energy level adds one hump. Thus the humps seem to represent spatial information about the level the wavefunction represents and also the possible decay routes. Again higher energy seems to imply more information and allows a certain energy wavefunction to be orthogonal to all wavefunctions with lower energy. Thus it needs to have spatial information about the energy eigenfunctions which come before it.

References

1. Ruggeri, Francesco R. Lagrangian/Action formalism as a flow scheme? (preprint, zenodo, 2021)